

EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING AND FINANCIAL OUTCOMES: A LITERATURE SYNTHESIS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relevance of social and environmental disclosure and financial performance. The systematic review of academic and professional literature depicts that social and environmental disclosure is very useful and significant in controlling entities that are operating in environmentally sensitive industries, and also in ensuring workers safety and good workplace practices. The research papers relating to the Social and environmental disclosures, which are available in Elsevier, Emerald, Wiley, Taylor and Francis, Sage and also MPDI, were used for this systematic review. The probability of published reports is a little bit unclear. Result show that studies on social and environmental disclosures is still evolving, and there is lack of consensus on the outcome of studies.

This is because while majority of the studies reviewed reported significant positive relationships between corporate social and environmental performance, others reported either negative relationships or mixed findings. Based on the above, there is need for more studies on social and environmental disclosures, especially in the developing countries as most of the studies on the topic are concentrated in China and advanced countries. The need for more studies on CSED cannot be over-emphasized as it tends to open more discuss as well as bringing more diverse views of scholars based on the result of new findings from different sectors, across different parts of the world.

Keywords: Social Disclosure, Environmental Disclosure, Financial Performance, Environmental Costs.

1. Introduction

It is no longer new that activities of corporations or business organizations though desirable because of the benefits accruable to an economy, it is not without undesirable effects as well. For instance, production of utilities requires raw materials, and raw materials and usage does not only deplete the natural resources but also contaminate the environment and caused environmental degradation.

While the business organization may be reporting huge profit from their operations, and the shareholders smiles to their banks after receiving their dividends, the opposite is faced by the community or the society where such companies produce because of the adverse effect of their production on the environment. These age-long issues have led to serious concerns by different stakeholders and this in turn led to societal concerns and awareness which culminated into demand for environmental accountability.

Firms' proactivity is required in such areas as ameliorating or cushioning the effect of destruction created by their operation on the environment, and this prompted the relevant stakeholders to demand for the commitment to greater accountability for social and environmental information with the goal of disseminating relevant information to varying stakeholders, (Okpala and Iredele, 2018). Obviously, the

connection mandatory disclosure and performance of companies is significant and correlated with key performance indicators for a business such as company size, profitability and leverage amongst others (Hieu et al, 2019).

Environmental disclosure is a means of revealing the environmental cost incurred for developmental initiatives, while social disclosure refers to the responsibility of organizations to share information relating to their social and environmental conservation activities, environmental impacts, social impacts, and performance with the aim of being accountable to the stakeholders. Also, environmental accounting can be described as a measure adopted by organizations and entities to discover more opportunities and environmental concerns, and putting same into strategic planning and decision, and as well making full disclosure of the issues identified, (Bailey and Soyka, 1996).

Environmental accounting presents a framework for business entities to recognize and provide due accountability for environmental costs, aimed at supporting management decision-making and public disclosure, (KPMG, 2006). This disclosure is necessary because environmental information helps the community or society and the firms to recognize the pivotal impacts of businesses on the environment. The extent of disclosing social and environmental issues positively or negatively affects financial performance of companies, and there is an increasing demand for such disclosures so as to ameliorate the adverse effects of business operations on the environment, because of relatively low level of disclosures against continuous agitations by environmental activist and relevant stakeholders. An empirical investigation into the level of disclosures, mandatory or voluntary disclosures is required especially in developing countries, particularly Sub-Saharan Africa. Therefore, this systematic literature review was carried out with the objective of enhancing awareness about the significance of social and environmental disclosures practices. In view of the above, this study intends to answer the following research questions as stated below:

RQ1: What are the publication trends in review-based studies on social and environmental disclosures in terms of the number of publications, prominent journals, authors and articles? RQ2: What are the major themes in review-based studies on social and environmental disclosures? RQ3: What are the practical implications and potential future directions of social and environmental disclosure?

2. Methodology

The current literature on the Social and Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance focuses on researching related academic papers instead of devising new theories. For this reason, the study made to use a systematic review strategy to identify and coordinate the current information for analysis. This methodology builds on research that draws on academic and primary sources by studying observational studies and peer reviewed journal papers. This research aims to produce a literature review and only legitimate journals used for its source. This article is based on the preferred reporting items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines. Describe this guideline, including the two steps: systematic literature review and content analysis briefly. Specific methods which this study follows is presented in section 2.1 by following the cited protocols. The study presented a content analysis to

recognize and for the organization of qualitative data from the literature for a better comprehension of Social and Environmental Disclosures.

Systematic Literature Review

The term used to find the literature was social and environmental disclosure and financial performance and used Elsevier, Sage, MPDI, Emerald, Wiley and Taylor and Francis journals to find the literature. These journals were used as they are large search systems that employ multiple databases. The database was covered the period between 2000 and 2025. In order to narrow the results to those published during the period, the date range was used. The research used only peerreviewed journal articles published in English. By using the same search terms in Google Scholar, search engines were browsed by using the key terms to the study: "Social and Environmental Disclosure and Financial performance", " These search methods recognized 1170 records in total research articles. Redundant studies were removed from the review, and further, some articles were applied the same framework, then those articles were excluded to prevent double counting. PRISMA flow diagram of the literature search and the review is presented as follows:

Identification

FIGURE 1 PRISMA FLOW DIAGRAM OF LITERATURE SEARCH AND REVIEW Content Analysis

34 sources were chosen for the investigation, and each source was read in full for qualitative content analysis. Information relating to Social and environmental disclosure and financial performance was recorded in a spreadsheet. It was organized into categories as author and year, title, scope, methodology, result, recommendation, and journal name. The information recognized from the literature was added to cells under the categories as identified by the researchers.

3. Results and Discussion

The articles reviewed and included in the study were sourced in Elsevier, Sage, MPDI, Emerald, Wiley and Taylor and Francis, are presented in table 1. The table centers on the title and reference of the research for each article.

Thematic Information on Social and Environmental disclosures and Financial Performance Table 1

Title	Reference/Source
Sustainable banking initiatives, environmental disclosure and financial performance: The moderating impact of corporate governance mechanisms	Adu, (2022)
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure Quality and Firm Financial Performance: Evidence from an Emerging Economy.	Alam and Tariq, (2022)
CSR disclosure and financial performance revisited: A crosscountry analysis.	Beck et al., (2018)
Does Environmental Information Disclosure Mitigate Corporate Risk? Evidence from China.	Chang et al., (2020)
Exploring the Moderating Role of Social and Ethical Practices in the Relationship between Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance: Evidence from ESG Companies.	Chouaibi et al., (2022)
The associations between environmental disclosures with financial performance, environmental performance, and firm value",	Deswanto and Siregar, (2018)
Corporate environmental disclosure associated with firm value? A multicountry study of Gulf Cooperation Council firms.	Gerged et al., (2021)
Does environmental information disclosure affect the performance of energyintensive firms' borrowing ability? Evidence from China	Hu et al., (2018)
The Relations Among Environmental, Social Disclosure, Sustainable Development and Firm Performance: Empirical Evidence From Mining Enterprises listed on the stock market in Vietnam,	Nguyen and Nguyen, (2023)
Disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Performance: Evidence from India.	Laskar and Maji, (2017)
Can social disclosure induce a better corporate social performance?,	Monteiro et al., (2023)
Corporate Environment Performance, Environmental Information Disclosure and Financial Performance: Evidence from China.	Li et al., (2021)
Corporate Social Responsibility Information Disclosure and Financial Performance: Is Green Technology Innovation a Missing Link?	Li et al., (2023)

The impact of environmental disclosure and the quality of financial disclosure and IT adoption on firm performance: Does corporate governance ensure sustainability?	Lin and Qamruzzaman, (2023)
Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance: A Quantile Regression Approach.	Liu et al., (2019)
Inclusive environmental disclosure practices and firm performance: The role of green supply chain management.	Longoni and Cagliano, (2018)
A study of the relationships among environmental performance, environmental disclosure, and financial performance.	Lu and Taylor, (2018)
Impact of Environmental Disclosure on Firm Performance: The Mediating Role of Green Innovation.	Malik et al., (2023)
Cooperative social and environmental disclosure and financial performance of savings and credit cooperatives in Kenya.	Mathuva and Kiweu, (2016)
The Effects of Environmental Disclosure on Financial Performance in Malaysia.	Nor et al., (2016)
The relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance of public listed companies in Malaysia. Journal of International Business Management, 10(4), 461-467.	Ong et al., (2016).
Investment in corporate social responsibility, disclosure practices, and financial performance of banks in Nigeria.	Oyewumi et al., (2018)
CSR disclosure and firm performance: The mediating role of corporate reputation and moderating role of CEO integrity.	Phama and Tranb, (2020)
The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure on Financial Performance: Evidence.	Platonova et al., (2018)
The effect of social responsibility disclosure on financial performance in the COVID-19 pandemic era.	Prayanthi and Budiarmo, (2022)

Environmental and social disclosures: Link with corporate financial performance.	Qiu et al., (2016)
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSRD) and Financial Distressed Risk (FDR): Does Institutional Ownership Matter?	Tarighi et al., (2022)
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Financial Performance: The Mediating Role of Financial Statement Comparability.	Thuy et al., (2021)
Quantifying the dynamics between environmental information disclosure and firms' financial performance using functional data analysis.	Wang et al., (2021)
Does environmental information disclosure contribute to improve firm financial performance? An examination of the underlying mechanism.	Wang et al., (2020)
The relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance: mediating effect of economic development and information penetration.	Wu and Li (2023)
The Impact of Environmental Information Disclosure in the "Carbon Trading Pilot" Project on the Financial Performance of Listed Enterprises in China.	Xu and Liu, (2024)
Environmental information disclosure and corporate performance: Evidence from Chinese listed companies. <i>Heliyon</i> 9 (2023) e22400.	Ye et al., (2023)
"Does Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure Improve Firm Investment Efficiency? Evidence from China",	Zhong and Gao, (2019)

The results from the review shows that Qui et al (2016) examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in China. Result shows that firms that make higher social disclosures have higher market values. Overall findings show that firms with greater economic resources make more extensive disclosures which yield net positive economic benefits.

Also, Nguyen and Nguyen (2023) examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in Vietnam and findings indicated that the level of environmental and social disclosure has direct impact on the level of sustainable development and firm performance. In the same vein, Ye et al (2023) examined environmental disclosures and corporate performance in China. The results revealed that EID can significantly improve corporate performance through green innovation (GI). Also, EID can enhance corporate GI, which improves the financial performance of high polluting firms and the environmental performance of non-high-polluting firms.

Similarly, Wang et al (2020) examined environmental disclosures and financial performance in China. The results revealed that environmental information disclosure positively (directly) affects financial performance. Further, environmental information disclosure also indirectly affects financial performance via analyst coverage and liquidity.

Furthermore, Li et al (2018) examined environmental information disclosures and financial performance in China. The results indicated that enterprise's environmental information disclosure appears to have a significantly positive effect on firm performance.

Also, Gerged et al (2021) examined the relationships between corporate environmental disclosures and financial performance in GCC countries. Result shows that CED is significantly and positively related to FV as measured by Tobin's Q (TBQ). Some evidence of a positive relationship between CED and return on assets is also found, but even where statistically significant, the relationship is much weaker than in the case of TBQ.

Similarly, Ika and Swandari (2022) in Indonesia found that the disclosure of social responsibility has a significant positive effect on return on assets. Also, social responsibility disclosure has a significant positive effect on return on equity.

Likewise Monteiro et al (2023) covering multinational countries, the study found that both total and partial disclosures of the performance indicators are positively associated with higher social performance.

In the same vein, Phama and Tran (2020) investigated corporate social disclosures and firm reputation in 31 countries. The paper shows a positive effect of CSR disclosure on firm reputation, which in turn significantly contributes to a firm's financial performance.

Also, Liu et al (2019) in Vietnam found that CSR disclosure has a positive impact on the financial performance of listed companies in Vietnam. Also, there is a complementary mediation effect of financial statement comparability in the above relationship.

In a similar move, Alam and Tariq (2019) from Pakistan found a positive significant relationship between CSR and accounting-based financial performance measured through return on assets. The relationship of CSR initiatives of the firms is also significantly related to market-based financial performance captured through Tobin's Q, indicating that the market is positively reacting to the CSR disclosure levels.

Furthermore, Li et al (2019) examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in China. The result shows that disclosure information of corporate social responsibility has a significant effect on enterprises' ROA. Secondly, there is a positive relationship between the shareholder responsibility score and employee responsibility score of information disclosure with financial performance. Thirdly, there is a significant positive correlation between the environmental responsibility score of CSR information disclosure with green technology innovation.

Also, Lascar and Maji (2017) examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in India. The results of the regression model indicate positive and significant impact of CSR (including its components) on firm performance.

According to Thuy et al., (2021) in Vietnam. CSR disclosure has a positive impact on the financial performance of listed companies in Vietnam. Second, there is a complementary mediation effect of financial statement comparability in the above relationship. This study examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance.

Similarly, Beck et al., (2018) also examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in Australia, Hongkong, and UK. The study finds a significant relationship between CSR engagement and financial performance, even after controlling for the CSR performance proxy, firm size, industry-level fixed effects, financial risk and type of assurer

Furthermore, Wu and Li (2023) examined corporate social and disclosures and financial performance in China, with a mediating effect of economic development and information penetration. Findings show that there is positive relationship between both mandatory environmental disclosure and voluntary environmental disclosure and financial performance; economic development positively relates to corporate financial performance, and it also strengthens the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance; information penetration positively relates to corporate financial performance.

In the same vein, Liu et al., (2019) examined corporate social disclosures and financial performance in China. It was found that CSR disclosure influences negatively financial performance. Further, CSR disclosure influences negatively financial constraints in financially opaque firms, and the effect of financial opaque on the relationship strengthens when the company faces great financial constraints.

Likewise Chang et al., (2020) examined environmental information disclosures and financial performance in China. Result shows that environmental information disclosure reduces firm investor information asymmetry, decreases uncertainties about assets pricing, and thus significantly decreases corporate risk.

Also, Chouaibi et al (2022) investigated environmental disclosures in Cross country. Results show a positive and significant relationship between environmental disclosure (ED) and financial performance (FP). This implies that a strong environmental disclosure increases financial performance while a weak one decreases it.

Furthermore, Lin and Qamruzzaman (2023) investigated environmental disclosures in Bangladesh. The study revealed a positive and statistically significant association between a firm's sustainability and target explanatory variables. Also, findings show a positive linkage between financial and environmental disclosure, IT adaptation, good governance, and the firm's performance sustainability.

Similarly, Adu (2022) examined environmental disclosures and sustainable banking initiatives, and financial performance in Sub-Saharan Africa. Findings of the study shows positive relationship between environmental disclosures and sustainable banking initiatives, and financial performance.

In the same vein, Wang et al (2021) investigated the relationships between environmental disclosures and financial performance in China. The results revealed a significant positive relationship between EID and firms' financial performance.

In another study, Longoni and Cagliana (2018) examined environmental disclosures and financial performance in Italy. Results revealed a significant effect of environmental disclosure practices on financial performance but no support for the impact on environmental performance. Specifically, the more inclusive the environmental disclosure practices the greater and positive is the impact on financial performance in presence of GSCM practices

Furthermore, Mathuva and Kiweu (2016) examined Corporate social disclosures in Kenya. The study revealed a negative association between CSED and financial performance.

Also, Nor et al (2016) investigated the relationships between environmental disclosures and financial performance in Malaysia. The analysis shows mixed results between the existence of the environmental disclosure practices in Malaysia and financial performance. There is significant but negative relationship between TED and financial performance indicator which is profit margin. Further results shows that there is significant relationship between TED and profit margin but there is no relationship with other three key indicators of financial performance.

Similarly, Xu and Liu (2024) examined environmental disclosures in China. The “Carbon Trading Pilot” policy-related environmental disclosure negatively affects enterprise financial performance; however, the environmental disclosure level is positively correlated with enterprise financial performance, and both impacts are heterogeneous. It also shows that studying the impact of environmental policies on enterprise financial performance is of paramount significance for economic sustainability.

Also, Lu and Taylor (2018) investigated environmental performance and financial performance in the U S. Findings from this study show a negative relationship between EP and FP and a positive relationship between EP and ED, suggesting that financially successful firms are less likely good environmental performers but green firms are more likely to disclose their EP.

In the same vein, Deswanto and Siregar (2018) in a study conducted on environmental disclosures in Indonesia found that the financial performance does not affect the environmental disclosures. The lagged environmental performance has a positive effect on the current environmental disclosures, and environmental disclosures do not affect the firm market value and do not mediate the effect of financial performance and environmental performance on firm value.

Also, Oyewumi et al (2018) in their study in Nigeria on corporate social disclosures and financial performance found that CSR investment without due disclosure would have little or no contribution to corporate financial performance.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined multiple Literatures with a focus on high impact journals from Elsevier, sage, Emerald, MPDI, Taylor and Francis, and Wiley. The focus was on social and environmental disclosures, and studies reviewed are from China, Vietnam, United States, Italy, Indonesia, Malaysia, India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nigeria, Kenya, Sub-Saharan Africa, GCC countries, while few others are from multiple countries. Result shows that studies on social and environmental disclosures is still evolving, and there is lack of consensus on the outcome of studies.

This is because while majority of the studies reviewed reported significant positive relationships between corporate social and environmental performance (Monteiro et al., 2023; Ye et al., 2023; Ika and Swandari, 2022; Wang et al., 2021; Gerged et al., 2021; Li et al., 2018; Qui et al., 2018 amongst numerous others), others reported either negative relationships (Liu et al., 2019 and Mathuva and Kiweu, 2016) or mixed

findings (Xu and Liu, 2024; Chouaibi et al, 2022; Deswanto and Siregar, 2018; Lu and Taylor, 2018; Oyewumi et al., 2018; Nor et al., 2016) etc.

Based on the above, there is need for more studies on social and environmental disclosures, especially in the developing countries as most of the studies on the topic are concentrated in China and advanced countries. The need for more studies on CSED cannot be over-emphasized as it ends to open more discuss as well as bringing more diverse views of scholars based on the result of new findings from different sectors, across different parts of the world.

Furthermore, this study suggest that further studies on CSED should focus on environmentally friendly or less sensitive companies, as social disclosures extend beyond harmful environmental practices only.

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